

Evaluating Study Of Lesson Plans At Primary Level Of Education

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Abstract

Government of Punjab issued lesson plan guides to all primary schools teachers, to know the outcomes of these lesson plans guides keeping in view their importance existing study intends to evaluate the quality of those lesson plans at primary level of education. The main intention of this study was to evaluate usefulness of teachers guides. The nature of existing study was descriptive while focusing the objectives study such as to examine the perception of head teachers and primary school teachers about availability, utilization and structure of lesson plans give in teachers guide. For this purpose one district from having more population and one district having less population from Punjab were selected as sample of study. From both districts 300 primary school teachers (150 from each district) and 100 head teachers (50 from each district) were taken as sample. Questionnaires were used for data collection and percentage was used for data analysis. Major conclusions were drawn about the execution and impacts of lesson plans guide on students learning after its issuance and utilization in class rooms teaching learning activities. Activity based teaching which plays vital role towards conceptual clarity, lifelong learning, learning by doing, learning by involving learners in teaching learning process, joyful learning environment in classrooms and improving the pedagogical skills of teachers after using lesson plans guides in their teaching learning practices in class rooms. Though most of the head teachers as well as teachers rendered their opinions that lesson plans promulgated in lesson plans guides are being used, available and executed in teaching learning activities in class rooms at primary level of education. But they recommended teachers guides may be issued frequently to all teachers as now these are issued only once. Further lesson planes do not fully cover the learning outcomes which given the text books therefore these lesson plans need revision and must have flexibility for teachers to plan their lessons for according to their text books and academic back ground.

Introduction

Education is learning process. Islam our religion stresses on learning, Holy Prophet (SAW) said, "It is obligatory for all Muslims to seek knowledge (Mishkat, p.157) Acquiring knowledge from birth to death is another saying of Prophet Muhammad (Peace Be upon Him).

Education prepares Youth which enhance their visions, respect to humanity and leads nations to meets global changes and challenges. Education is a unique source for transmitting values from one generation to another. Islam and all religions stressed for promoting effective teaching and learning practices. In Pakistan lot of efforts have been made to meet challenges of era and enhance practices of quality education at all level through teaching and learning process to meet sustainability and the global goals for quality education .

To enhance quality of learning in classrooms planning at the end of teachers cannot be denied, planning enables teachers to meet assigned targets, educational goals, and drive their students towards future track. For delivering effective teaching, lesson planning plays a key role towards teachers. When the teachers are adept in lesson planning they can deliver effective lessons in classrooms, can manage time and resources effectively by using and inculcating child centered teaching and learning activities which leads students towards conceptual clarity, and lifelong learning.

Planning of lesson may lead teacher to deliver his sessions in time, boosts pedagogical skills of teachers, create interesting learning context and activity based teaching learning practices which focus on learning by doing, increasing students interest and full involvement in learning.

Hence planning of lesson plays a vital role to achieve optimum goals and objectives in classrooms. Stress for effective Planning of lesson owing to its pivotal role in teaching and learning process has always been given at all teacher education and training institutions in the world. All efforts in classrooms teaching learning process revolves around the lesson plan. It has been observed that if teachers have competency in planning then it leads them to perform their effective professional tasks in classrooms. Promoting effective

learning practices which meets their desired goals and leads towards quality education. Lesson plan is road map for teachers which leads them to complete their tasks effectively and timely.

Successfully planned lesson plays an important role and is heart of effective teaching, which leads teachers to gather many factors such as knowledge, pedagogical skills, competencies, nature of subject, and teacher's beliefs towards the subject, its teaching style, social and cultural context in classrooms and format of lesson plan. Nevertheless, if teachers put sincere efforts towards lesson plan then classrooms activities can lead towards effective and fruitful learning. Properly and effectively planned lessons leads towards efficacy in teaching learning practices. (Cuban 2000; Cohen 1990; Cohen and Ball 1990; Cuban 1990; Tyack and Cuban 1998).

Keeping in view the importance of lesson plan, government of Punjab issued lesson plan guides to all primary schools teachers in Punjab, to enhance their pedagogical skills, activity based teaching learning practices in classrooms. In current study efforts have been made to evaluate the structure, quality and alignment of lesson plans according the requirements of text books and teaching learning parameters of primary level of education particularly in Punjab.

STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

For making the teaching learning process effective, interactive and interactive lesson plans play an important role which makes the teacher well conversant about the teaching learning needs. For this purpose efforts of Punjab government are commendable about preparing and providing the teachers' guides comprise on lesson plans at primary level. The question arises about the quality of those lesson plans either are useful or not. For probing this answer an evaluating the study of lesson plans at primary level of education was conducted.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Following objective of this study was focused:

1. To examine the opinions of head teachers and primary school teachers about quality, relevance, structure, availability and usability of lesson plans given in teachers' guides.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Benefits of well prepared lesson plan cannot be denied. Success in classrooms teaching learning process leads to well planned lesson..It is established fact that students always get lot of benefits from teachers who have planned their lessons well.

Researches show that students get benefit as well as appreciate to effectively -structured lessons. (Kizlik, 2010). Students who are deemed as keen observer in classrooms, learn more from effectively planned lessons. They mainly know that either teachers are fully prepare or not. Today our students seem for having need about invariable momentum or stimulation (Marcotte, 2010). When "down time" and hesitation at the part of teachers who are struggling to decide about their work to do, so students can move rapidly from being on-track to off as well as away from at hand assignments .. Teachers who have planned well seem likely towards attentive students. Context which assist them more attentive surly is helpful towards students from efficiently planned lessons, they will focus towards lesson to achieve objectives which are at hand and teacher is striving in classrooms to achieve them.. On the other hand if a teachers who has been teaching without a planned lesson dream of success in classrooms cannot be reached as a result teachers will rapidly become distracted from student behavior, threatening responsibilities, along with other variables which are present in each classroom.

Obviously Students gets benefit from those teachers who have proficiency in lesson planning which relates assessment to achieve objectives meaningfully. Well planned lesson permits students for assessing fairly. Effective planning of lesson leads towards effective classroom assessment of students to know the level of achievements directly reproduce desired objective in student for which teacher is striving for, what they have been actually taught. Well planned and prepared lesson, reflects interests as well as requirements of students. It includes best practices towards educational field. Lot of things are taking places simultaneously in the Classrooms, so classrooms places full with activities. Teachers faces challenged in classrooms for monitoring multiple actions simultaneously which have been collecting as well as analyzing data regarding students' performance.

Lesson plan is important elements for classrooms activities which provided lot of benefits. As teachers become adept in developing their lesson plan at that time they become aware about the content and methods to be used in classrooms (Kizlik, 2010)

Effectively planned lessons promotes efficacy at the part of teachers towards classrooms activities, (Cuban 2000; Cohen 1990; Cohen and Ball 1990; Cuban 1990; Tyack and Cuban 1998).

. Ralph Tyler who has been deemed as an expert for effective institutional organizations to meet planned learning out comes and gain educational objectives of institutions states following steps:-

- a) Specify of learning out comes
 b) choosing of teaching learning activities
 c) Arrangements of learning activities and
 d) Recognize evaluation process (Doyle & Holm, 1998).

It is an admitted fact that in teaching learning process stress always exists and it has remained an effective element. All efforts which a teacher does to reduce stress are optimistic pace towards accurate way. McDonald, co-author of Survival tips towards novice Teachers (2006), "An important and effective habit to reduce the quantity of stress, one's contract with everyday foundation is readiness." Support, assistance and time which teachers provided for lesson plan. Institutions must have an eye on teachers how much time teachers utilized on planning and then for rendering their active professional tasks in classrooms.

Lesson plan correlates teaching learning activities with text book which class uses. Text books are mainly chosen by teachers.

Owing to unique importance of lesson plan towards effective deliverance, enhance activity based teaching practices, promote interest, leads learners towards clarity of concepts, meeting global challenges and changes, and enhance learners interest towards learning by doing, creating such context in classrooms in which all sorts may participate, government of Punjab issued lesson plan guides to all primary teachers teaching at primary level of education. In current students efforts has been made for evaluating of lesson plans at primary level of education.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study was delimited to only those lesson plans guides which were provided to teachers at primary system of education in public schools of Punjab.

RESAERCH METHODOLOGY

The prime objective of this study was to know the important input of all lesson plan as well as its guides for enhancing quality of education at primary level in public schools of Punjab. Current study dealt with recent situation regarding implementation of lesson plans so it was descriptive in nature and survey method was used. With intention towards comprehending effectiveness of lesson plans self-developed questionnaires for head teachers and teachers of primary schools were used. Overall methodology of existing study comprised on population, sample, research instrument, collection of data and its analysis.

i. Population

Keeping in view the limitation of researcher only 18 districts out of 36 districts Punjab were taken as target population of the study. From these selected districts 9 districts most populated and 9 districts less populated from all divisions were focused. Total number of primary schools is 17789 male and 19070 female. From most populated district Multan district and from less populated district Bahawalnagar were selected as target population of the study. Total number of primary school of Multan was 1548 and total number of teachers of these schools was 7461 while total number of primary school of Bahawalnagar was 869 and total number of teachers of these school was 4032.

ii. Sample

From target population two districts, one most populated and one less populated were selected through random sampling technique. Hence Multan is most populated while

Bahawalnagar is less populated district. Then from these districts 100 primary schools 50 from each district were also selected randomly. From these 100 schools 300 teachers teaching at primary level 3 teachers from each school selected randomly. And all 100 head teachers were taken as sample of study. Sample of study may be given as under:

Nature of District	District Name	No of Schools	No of Teachers	No of Head Teachers
Most populated	Multan	50	150(50x3)	50
Less populated	Bahawalnagar	50	150(50x3)	50
Total	02	100	300	100

iii. Instruments

Keeping in view the nature of existing study two questionnaires on three point scale as instruments of survey were used. One questionnaire was used for head teachers and one for used for primary school teachers. Researcher developed these questionnaires on three point scale as agree, to some extent and not at all. During the development of these questionnaires main aspects related to lesson plans as given in teachers' guides were focused such as availability, usability, significance, enhancing teaching learning quality, improving students, results, focusing students learning outcomes, structure of lesson plan, time management availabilities of A.V aids etc were focused.

iv. Data Collection

Researcher himself and with the help of representative from far flung areas visited of sampled school and distributed the questionnaires among the head teachers and primary school teachers and collected the data. Therefore 100% questionnaires got filled and received back.

RESULTS

A. Questionnaire for Head Teachers' analysis

- 80% head teachers agreed that lesson plan guides are available in schools with all teachers while 12% stated to some extent available and 8% stated that not at all available.
- 86% head teachers agreed that all teachers at primary level have lesson issued with plan guides while 6% stated as to some extent have been issued with lesson plans guides and 8% stated that not at all have been issued to all teachers lesson plans guides.
- 77% head teachers agreed that lesson plan guides benefitted primary school teachers towards quality education while 12% head teacher stated to some extent and 11% stated as not at all.
- 72% head teachers agreed that lesson plans guides have been maintained in best state in schools while 13% stated as to some extent and 15% stated as not at all.
- 75% head teachers agreed that teachers generally perceive lesson plans guides while 13% stated as to some extent and 12% stated as not at all.
- 82% head teachers agreed that generally lesson plans guides facilitate teachers towards easiness as well as quality in their work while 11% stated as to some extent and 7% stated as not at all.
- 84% head teachers agreed that teacher prepare lesson plans from lesson plan guides while 12% stated as to some extent and 06% stated as not at all.
- 79% head teachers agreed that lesson plan guides are helpful to teachers for structuring their own lesson plans while 12% stated as to some extent and 9% stated as not at all.
- 83% head teachers agreed that teachers generally reports regarding benefits of lesson plans guides while 7% stated as to some extent and 10% stated as not at all.
- 82% head teachers agreed that lesson plan guides are a reference book for teachers while 8% states as to some extent and 10% stated as not at all.
- 84% head teachers agreed that at primary level lesson plan guides are considered as hand out for teachers while 11% stated as to some extent and 5% stated as not at all.
- 83% head teachers agreed that Punjab examination commission results have been increased after lesson plan guides while 8% stated as to some extent and 9% stated as not at all.

13. 85% head teachers agreed that after lesson plans guides monthly assessment results have been increase while 7% stated as to some extent and 8% stated as not at all.
14. 72% head teachers agreed that level of students and lesson plan guided coordinate while 7% reflected as to some extent and 21% stated as not at all.
15. 58% head teachers agreed that language used in lesson plan guides also meet level of primary schools teachers while 22% stated as to some extent and 30% stated as not at all.
16. 83% head teachers agreed that lesson plan guides are used by teachers during their professional development days to enhance pedagogical skills while 22% Stated as to some extent and 7% stated not at all.
17. 88% head teachers agreed that lesson plans guides have increased activity based teaching context in teaching learning process while 7% stated as to some extent and 5% stated not at all.
18. 76% head teachers agreed that teaching aids described in lesson plan guides are reachable and available to teachers while 14% stated to some extent and 10% stated not at all.
19. 75% head teachers agreed that lesson plan guides are helpful to teachers at primary level while 11% stated as to some extent and 14% stated as not at all.

20. 74% head teachers agreed that activities mentioned in lesson plan guides are according to the context of learners while 12% stated to some extent and 14% stated not at all.
21. 78% head teachers agreed that activities described in lesson plan guides are easily executed by teachers during their teaching at primary level while 13% stated to some extent and 9% stated as not at all.

B. Questionnaire for Primary School Teachers' Analysis

1. 75% teachers agreed that lesson executed as per lesson plan guides make easiness and quality in teachers work while 13% stated to some extent and 12% stated as not at all.
2. 78% teachers agreed that after using teacher guide lesson plan practices towards quality education has been increased in classrooms while 10% stated to some extent and 12% stated as not at all.
3. 71% teachers agreed that interest in students after using teacher guide lesson plans by teachers in their teachings has been increased while 15% stated to some extent and 14% stated as not at all.
4. 69% teachers agreed that lesson plans always facilitates teachers to support activity based teaching activities in classrooms while 14% stated to some extent and 17% stated as not at all.
5. 76% teachers agreed as lesson plans are only helpful for newly inducted teachers while 13% stated as to some extent and 11% stated as not at all.
6. 78% teachers agreed that only experienced teachers can get benefits from lesson plan guides while 15% stated to some extent and 7% stated as not at all.
7. 65% teachers agreed as lesson plan covers all sort of SLOs while 12% stated to some extent and 23% stated as not at all.
8. 74% teachers agreed that increase in activity based teaching learning practices in classrooms are attributed to use of teacher guides lesson plans by teachers in their teachings while 9% stated to some extent and 17% as not at all.
9. 72% teachers agreed that lesson plans meet needs of all level of students while 15% state to some extent and 13% stated not at all.
10. 82% teachers agreed that language used in lesson plans guides meet the level of all primary schools teachers while 13% to some extent and 15% stated as not at all.
11. 81% teachers agreed that pedagogical skills of teachers have been increased after using lesson plan guides while 14% stated to some extent and 15% stated as not at all.
12. 67% teachers agreed that practicality of lesson plan guides can be measured while 16% stated to some extent and 17% stated as not at all.
13. 84% teachers agreed that teaching aids described in lesson plan guides are easily available while 17% to some extent and 9% stated not at all.
14. 79% teachers agreed that pictorial work of lesson plan guides is facilitating teachers during their teachings while 14% to stated to some extent and 17% stated not at all.
15. 74% teachers agreed pictorial work in teacher guide lesson plans has improved interest of learners while 16% stated to some extent and 10% stated not at all.
16. 84% teachers agreed that activities mentioned in lesson plan guide can be executed easily while 12% stated to some extent and 14% stated not at all.
17. 83% teachers agreed that lesson plan guides covers all SLOs given in text books while 13% stated to some extent and 14% stated not at all.

18. 81% teachers agreed that lesson plan can be described as curriculum extended approach while 12% stated to some extent and 17% stated not at all.
19. 84% teachers agreed that after using teachers guide lesson plans teachers have been writing their own lesson plans while 14% stated to some extent and 12% stated not at all.
20. 84% teachers agreed that composition of lesson plans guides is according to taleemi calendar while 13% stated to some extent and 3% stated not at all.
21. 85% teachers agreed that monthly assessment results by DTEs have been increased after using lesson plan guides while 11% stated to some extent and 4% stated as not at all.
22. 76% teachers agreed that all activities mentioned in lesson plans are according to environment of learners while 13% stated to some extent and 11% stated as not at all.
23. 73% teachers agreed that structuring of lesson plans meets required standards while 12% stated to some extent and 15% stated not at all.

CONCLUSIONS

Many head teachers reflected as lesson plan constructed in Lesson plan guides are being assisted and supported in primary schools teaching learning activities. Great number of teachers supported that lesson plans mentioned in Lesson plan guides have been supplied to all teachers are being implemented, used and utilized in daily class rooms teaching learning activities and are available with teachers during playing their active professional tasks in classrooms. Most head teachers and teachers stated that pictorial work stated in lesson plans creates interest in students, easiness and quality in the work of teachers. Many head teachers and teachers opted that audio visual aids mentioned in lesson plans guides are easily available and are relevant to learner context. On basis of the results following conclusions have been drawn:

1. Lesson plans are being used and observed by teachers during their teaching in classrooms.
2. Lesson plans are facilitating teachers towards their teaching learning practices in classrooms
3. Primary teachers are using lesson plans but their difficulty level has been reported by the teachers.
4. Lesson plans improved activity based teaching learning practices in classrooms.
5. Lesson plans have lead teachers towards effective teaching learning activities in classrooms practices..
6. Lesson plans of teachers' guides created activity based, teaching learning environment in schools.
7. Lesson plans enhanced activity based and child centered teaching learning activities in schools.
8. Time management by the teachers during their sessions is another attribute of Lesson plans.
9. Teaching learning activities have been increased after using lesson plans by the teachers during their teaching at primary level of education.
10. Teaching aids can be easily arranged by the teachers as mentioned in lesson plans.
11. Clarity of concepts in students accredited through using Lesson plans by the teachers during their teaching.
12. Joy full teaching learning activities in classrooms were assured after using lesson plans by the teachers.
13. Effective teaching of teachers was asserted owing to use of lesson plans by them.
14. Life- long learning and quality education in classrooms was also assured is through lesson plans guide being used by teachers teaching at primary level of education.
15. Lesson plans promoted activity based teaching learning practices which involved all learners during teaching.
16. Lesson plans motivated teachers for structuring their own lesson plans.
17. Lesson plan also motivated the teachers for enhancing class/and home work activities.
18. Improvement in students learning and monthly assessment results was ascertained due to use of lesson plans by the teachers teaching at primary level of education.
19. Different activities mentioned in lesson plans enhanced the interest among learners towards their learning and enhanced pedagogical skills of teachers.
20. Lesson Plans fulfilled the students learning out comes mentioned in text book.
21. Lesson plans are compatible with the content of text books taught at primary level.
22. Activities mentioned in Lesson Plan enhanced students scientific, linguistic and mathematical skills.
23. Lesson plans lead teachers towards students centered and activity based teaching learning process.
24. Interest in students towards their learning by doing was examined after using the lesson plans.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of results and conclusions of this study following recommendations were drawn:

1. Lesson plans are mostly available for head teacher and not available for all teachers therefore availability of lesson plans teachers' guides for all may be ensured.

2. It was also opined that lesson plans teachers' guide were issued only once, if new teachers are inducted these were not issued to them. Therefore there should be a proper mechanism for frequent issuance of lesson plans teachers' guides.
3. It was recommended that mostly plans do not fulfill the learning outcomes of text books taught at primary level therefore revision should be made according to the content.
4. Keeping in view the qualification back ground of primary school teachers the language of lesson plans given in teachers' guide may be simplified after revision. As mostly teachers have the medium of instruction was Urdu.
5. Lesson plans may be prepared for all subjects are being taught at primary level currently these are about only English, Science and Mathematics.
6. All the teacher training programs of all institution may focus the importance of lesson plans during the training of teachers for making them well conversant about planning their lesson during career.

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